

Mitigation of Humidity Interference by Graphene Derivatives for Efficient Temperature Sensors without Encapsulation

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Temperature monitoring and regulation are essential in various environments, including modern industry and living and storage spaces. The growing demand for temperature sensors calls for affordable, efficient, interference-resistant, and eco-friendly solutions. The challenge of humidity interference in constructing temperature sensors often leads to compromising on the dynamic sensor properties in particular due to the need for encapsulation. To this end, this study introduces a temperature sensor leveraging a carefully designed graphene derivative to mitigate the humidity interference. The material, synthesized through scalable fluorographene chemistry with benzylamine, is optimized in order to enhance its properties, which led to achieving peak efficiency with a minimal humidity impact. The sensor demonstrated full functionality across a temperature range from 10 to 90 °C, with a temperature coefficient of resistivity $8.63 \times 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which is more than twice as high as that of conventional platinum thermometers. Remarkably, the sensor exhibited only a 2% change in resistance when exposed to relative humidity in the range of 20 to 70%. Notably, the sensor continues to give a consistent performance even after six months, which proved its stability. The presented device holds promise for evolving into a fully printed, cost-effective and reliable next-generation temperature sensors.

1. Introduction

Modern buildings, factories, stores, warehouses, distribution centers, and logistic terminals require highly precise and narrow controlling of temperature and humidity. These conditions, together with other requirements, ensure the comfort, health, and productivity of the occupants inside the buildings while also preventing the growth of mold, bacteria or viruses.^[1,2] For companies manufacturing, e.g., pharmaceuticals, chemicals, metal or paper, the temperature and humidity range is crucial as it impacts various aspects. These include the quality, stability, and safety of the products, as well as the performance, efficiency, and waste reduction of the processes. Additionally, it affects the life and maintenance of the machinery and equipment, alongside the well-being and safety of the workers. In handling hubs, they contribute to protection and prevention of damage, spoilage, or loss

of the products, the efficiency and reliability of the transportation, and delivery of the products.^[3] The recommended temperature and relative humidity inside the above-mentioned facilities are rather narrow, ranging from 15 to 25 °C and from 30 to 60%.^[4–6]

Humans have developed many sophisticated technologies for temperature regulation, which require reliable and robust temperature sensors. Several materials, such as ceramics,^[7–9] various polymers,^[10,11] semiconductors,^[12,13] and carbon-based allotropes,^[14–20] offer unique advantages, including rapid response, thermal stability, and suitability for wearable electronics. Among these, 2D layered materials stand out thanks to their large surface-to-volume ratio, excellent electronic properties, and exceptional mechanical characteristics.^[21–23] One of the standouts is the remarkable thermal conductivity of graphene, surpassing that of metals' and carbon nanotubes'.^[24] Additionally, it exhibits ultra-high carrier mobility, ensuring rapid response to temperature fluctuations.^[14] Furthermore, researchers have observed that single-layer graphene (SLG) has a negative temperature coefficient (NTC), meaning that its resistance decreases as temperature rises while demonstrating favorable semiconductor properties.^[25] The combination of these properties makes graphene an excellent candidate for temperature-sensing applications.^[26–29]

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DOI: 10.1002/aelm.202400052

However, a significant drawback is its susceptibility to humidity, which adversely affects temperature measurements when graphene is used as a sensing platform.^[30,31] This issue arises from the presence of oxygen groups on a graphene's surface, which can interact with water molecules, making the resulting temperature sensitivity detrimental.^[31,32] Several methodologies have been proposed to address this challenge, such as encapsulation,^[33–35] or the addition of protective agents like polydimethylsiloxane.^[30] However, several drawbacks are associated with these encapsulation approaches. For example, materials used for encapsulation often possess low thermal conductivity, which can impair the sensor's performance. This results in diminished accuracy and slower response times.^[36] Over time, these materials may allow humidity to penetrate, which causes sensor drift and potential failure. The additional thermal insulation provided by these materials can also delay the sensor's responsiveness to changes in environmental temperatures, thus reducing its effectiveness in dynamic conditions.^[37] Furthermore, the long-term stability and reliability of encapsulated sensors may deteriorate under fluctuating environmental conditions, which negatively impacts their overall performance.^[38]

Given these challenges, the focus is increasingly shifting toward finding novel materials that combine high dynamic range, stability, and affordability while also being resistant to humidity. These materials are crucial for advancing temperature sensing technology as their enhanced performance will circumvent the drawbacks associated with current materials. Graphene derivatization can enable such materials. However, direct functionalization of graphene presents significant challenges due to its inert basal plane and the absence of reactive functional groups, making chemical attachment difficult. The strong carbon–carbon bonds in graphene's hexagonal lattice structure contribute to its chemical inertness, hindering the direct addition of other atoms or molecules.^[39,40] To overcome the outlined challenges, we designed a graphene derivative, based on the principles of fluorographene chemistry, enhanced with covalently bonded benzylamine.^[41,42] This approach facilitates the scalable synthesis of graphene-based derivatives, allowing precise control over the incorporation of specific functional groups suitable for diverse applications.^[42–44] Chemistry-wise, fluorographene acts as an electrophile, easily engaging in reactions with nucleophiles—often under gentle conditions.^[45,46] The reactivity of fluorographene is thought to stem from radical point defects that initiate a series of nucleophilic substitution (S_N) reactions, accompanied by simultaneous defluorination.^[47] The resulting graphene derivatives demonstrate a low fluorine atom content yet exhibit well-defined functionalities and a notable degree of functionalization.^[42] Comprising both sp^2 and sp^3 carbon atoms, these derivatives possess sufficient conductivity, making them suitable for applications as sensor materials. In the context of temperature sensing, our hypothesis centered on the incorporation of a humidity-indifferent element, such as a benzene ring, onto the conductive substrate (in this case, the graphene structure). This strategic addition is anticipated to provide advantages by mitigating interactions with water molecules.^[31]

In this study, we synthesized a series of novel benzylamine (BZA) functionalized graphene derivatives via fluorographene chemistry, whose composition was controlled by reaction conditions. The sensors were fabricated using the printing of the

synthesized materials, and their performance was thoroughly tested. The sensor fabricated with a derivative containing the most attached benzylamine groups exhibited the most favorable response. Further, it displayed sensitivity to temperature changes while maintaining low sensitivity to humidity. Operating seamlessly across a broad temperature spectrum, from 10 to 90 °C, the sensor showed a temperature coefficient of resistivity $8.63 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ —more than double the performance of conventional platinum thermometers, meaning the developed sensor perfectly meets the industrial requirements for modern facilities. Furthermore, the sensor exhibited a minimal 2% relative change in resistance when subjected to humidity levels ranging from 20 to 70%. The exceptional performance and stability of our sensor, coupled with its potential for cost-effective production and scalability, suggest strong commercial applications in various fields where precise temperature monitoring is crucial.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Benzylamine Functionalized Graphenes with Controlled Degree of Functionalization

We employed fluorographene chemistry for the synthesis of new graphene derivatives covalently functionalized with BZA moieties as active materials for thermal sensors. The degree of functionalization was controlled by varying the molar ratio between the GF and BZA during the reaction. BZA was chosen due to its hydrophobic benzene ring, which can impart water-repellent properties to the material, necessary for reducing the temperature sensor interference with relative humidity. Additionally, the simplicity of such a molecule without additional functional groups, as reported here,^[48] is crucial to avoiding the trapping of the water molecules and, therefore, to yielding humidity resistance. It is noteworthy that the BZA played a dual role in the reaction—facilitating the fluorine removal from fluorographene and aiding the grafting of the BZA moieties on the graphene skeleton via the so-called “proton-coupled electron transfer”, as described in more detail by Siedle et al.^[49]

Our synthetic procedure builds on the very well-established wet chemistry routes using partially defluorinated fluorographene via the reaction in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) as a precursor for covalently grafting different moieties.^[45,50–54] The exfoliation and partial defluorination of the precursor was induced by initial stirring and sonication in dimethylformamide in order to increase the sp^2 carbon content in the final materials, which also increased their conductivity, followed by the addition of benzylamine. In order to investigate the influence of the number of the attached functional groups, three different benzylamine functionalized derivatives were prepared.

The prepared graphene derivatives were thoroughly characterized. An X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis confirmed the successful defluorination of the precursor, as evidenced by a significant reduction in the fluorine (F) atom content (**Figure 1a,b**). Specifically, the initial fluorine content, measured at 50.5 at.% (ref^[51]), decreased to 27.7 at.% for G-B0.5, 12.4 at.% for G-B1, and 6.2 at.% for G-B2. The opposite trend was observed for the carbon (C) content, when more carbons were added to the system as more benzylamine functionalities were attached. The same phenomenon was observed also for the overall

Figure 1. Synthesis and characterization of the graphene derivatives. a) XPS survey spectra, b) bar graph with an elemental composition determined by XPS, c) FT-IR, and d) Raman spectra of the three differently functionalized graphene derivatives, G-B0.5, G-B1, and G-B2. e-g) Scanning electron microscopy images of the G-B0.5, G-B1, and G-B2 derivatives, respectively, indicate a few-layered structure of graphene flakes with a lateral size in the 2–3 micrometers range.

defluorination, making carbon a major element in the materials. Furthermore, the covalent attachment of BZA was also verified by the increasing nitrogen (N) content in the graphene derivatives. The small oxygen content (≈ 3 at.%) in all samples comes from the reaction performed under air conditions.^[51] Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) measurements (Figure 1c) corroborated the XPS findings; the sharp peak observed at 1200 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C-F vibrations, exhibited reduced intensity with increasing BZA ratios. The broad peak observed below 1250 cm^{-1} encompassed contributions from C-F, C-N, C-C stretching, and C-O species, typically present moieties in graphene-based derivatives prepared via fluorographene chemistry.^[55] Moreover, the band at 700 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the C-H stretching, further supporting the successful covalent grafting of BZA.^[49] The Raman spectra (Figure 1d) of the synthesized derivatives displayed broad D and G bands at 1300 and 1590 cm^{-1} , respectively, with an almost identical I_D/I_G ratio of ≈ 1.1 while the parent fluorographene is a Raman silent material. This observation suggests a progressive elimination and concurrent replacement of fluorine atoms with BZA moieties while maintaining nearly unchanged ratios of sp^2 and sp^3 carbon groups^[53,56] within the pre-

pared derivatives. Furthermore, the increased intensity of the D-band, as evidenced by an I_D/I_G ratio of given G-B samples, implies the existence of atomic-scale defects like vacancies and grain boundaries,^[57] which is the common phenomenon observable in graphene derivatives that are extensively functionalized.^[58] An examination of the structural attributes and morphology of the prepared derivatives was performed to obtain insights into their suitability as effective thermal sensors. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed to reveal a planar, few-layered structure of graphene flakes, characterized by a relatively uniform size distribution falling within the 2–3 micrometers range. (Figure 1e–g SEM images). Such a morphology is expected for the derivatives prepared via a chemistry route,^[45,50] and provides sufficient conductivity and applicability of the prepared derivatives as thermal sensors.

2.2. Measurement of Conductivity of Benzylamine Functionalized Graphenes

The resistivity of the resulting material varied depending on the amount of benzylamine in the graphene structure. The resistivity

Figure 2. Summary of relative responses (see Equation 3) of the sensors to temperature step change a) G-B0.5, b) G-B1 and c) G-B2 and logarithm of resistivity versus reciprocal temperature d) G-B0.5 e) G-B1 and f) G-B2.

decreased with an increasing amount of BZA. There was a significant difference between the G-B0.5 and G-B1 sample, where the resistivity decreased by four orders of magnitude, from 23 864.6 to 2.532 $\Omega \cdot \text{m}$. Further addition of benzylamine to the graphene structure, in the case of the G-B2 sample, caused less than one order of magnitude decrease, to 0.363 $\Omega \cdot \text{m}$. More details about the resistivity measurements are provided in Supporting Information. To assess the trend observed through the four-point-probe measurement, we employed cyclic voltammetry, as depicted in Figure S4 (Supporting Information). The obtained results clearly indicate that after modifying the working electrode with the G-B samples, the current response of the ferricyanide probe significantly increased, compared to the non-modified electrode, confirming the trend observed using the four-point probe. It is evident that the conductive properties of the graphene benzylamine derivatives can substantially enhance the electron transfer, thereby reducing the resistance of the electrode sys-

tem. Our results show that the graphene derivatives prepared for this study are a conductive substrate with water-resilient groups on its surface. Unlike the fluorographene precursor, which is an insulator with fluorine groups enabling the attachment of water molecules via hydrogen bonds, the moieties on the G-BZA derivatives did not favor an interaction with water molecules.

2.3. Temperature Dependences of Graphene-Derivative-Based Sensors

The evaluation of the prepared derivatives as active materials for thermal sensors was performed while subjecting them to temperature profile testing, thus assessing their responses and material characteristics. The prepared sensors were exposed to a temperature profile, which consisted of a gradual increase in

temperature, from 10 to 90 °C in 10 °C increments. The sensor remained at each temperature value for 10 min to achieve a steady state value and returned back to 25 °C at the end of the cycle. The resulting sensors responses (relative change in resistance) to the test cycle are shown in **Figure 2a–c**. The overall sensor response was almost identical for the G-B1 and G-B2 materials, –68.4% and –69.6%, respectively. The repeatability of the G-B2 sensor response to temperature changes is shown in the Supporting Information (**Figure S8a**, Supporting Information). In the case of the G-B0.5 material, the response was higher at –76.6%. It should be noted that this and all the other properties of this sensor were determined in the range of 20 to 90 °C due to the indeterminate behavior of this material in the region of 10 to 20 °C, which is evident from **Figure 2a**. The cause of this behavior is the condensation of water molecules on the sensor surface at these temperatures and the moisture dependence of the G-B0.5 material, which is discussed in Section 2.5. The temperature dependence of this material measured at 0% RH, which confirms the above statement, can be found in Supporting Information (**Figure S2**, Supporting Information). All the tested samples showed exponential decreasing dependence, i.e., as the temperature increases, the resistance of the sensor decreases, which is typical for semiconductors-based thermistors.^[59] This means that these active sensor layers are semiconductors by nature. The reason is that the structure of the graphene-based layers is made of small, disordered graphene particles. Continuous pristine graphene, consisting of one or a few atomic layers without significant defects, exhibits a zero bandgap. Consequently, under certain conditions, it behaves as a semimetal, where the temperature-dependent resistance is primarily affected by electron-phonon scattering.^[60] As the temperature rises, the probability of charge carrier scattering also increases, leading to reduced charge carrier mobility and a subsequent increase in electrical resistance.^[61]

The tested materials were in the form of flakes, as confirmed by SEM in **Figure 1e–g**. Therefore, various other types of scattering, such as scattering on defects, impurities, flake edges, and multilayer structures, became prominent and dominated over the electron–phonon scattering. This led to a change from zero-bandgap graphene to a finite-gap semiconductor-like graphene.^[62] The thermally activated charge carriers determined the temperature dependence of resistance in these modified materials. As the temperature climbed, the probability of charge carriers transferring from the valence band to the conduction band increased, leading to a decrease in resistance.^[61]

Considering the nonlinear characteristics of the R–T dependence and the operating temperature (above 250 K), we can build

Table 1. Summary of key properties of the sensors.

Material	G-B0.5	G-B1	G-B2
T Response 10–90 °C (%)	–76.6	–68.4	–69.1
Response to 20–70% RH (%)	–32.9	–5.4	–2
Thermistor constant B (K)	2147.5	1482.7	1507.2
TCR (K ^{–1})	–10.2 × 10 ^{–3}	–8.29 × 10 ^{–3}	–8.63 × 10 ^{–3}
Resistivity (Ω•m)	23 864.6	2.53	0.36

Table 2. Comparison of TCR parameters of graphene-based temperature sensors. GO stands for graphene oxide, and r-GO for reduced GO.

Material	Temperature range [°C]	TCR [K ^{–1}]	Refs.
r-GO	30–100	–0.0063	GuanYu ^[61]
Single layer graphene	10–30	0.0022	Davaji ^[65]
r-GO	30–100	–0.008	Sehrawati ^[60]
Thermally reduced GO	20–180	–0.0148	Zunino ^[64]
Tri-layer graphene	30–70	–0.0017	Rajan ^[66]
Graphene nanoplatelets	10–100	–0.0052	Štulíček ^[37]
Laser-patterned graphene	30–100	–0.0018	Tripathi ^[67]
Graphene nanoplatelets	–60–60	–0.0016	Bertocchi ^[68]
Graphene – benzylamine	10–90	–0.0086	This work

a model of the sensor behavior according to the Arrhenius Equation 1), which is expressed as follows:

$$R = R_0 e^{-E_a/k_b T} \quad (1)$$

where R is the resistance at temperature T , R_0 is the resistance at infinite temperature, E_a is the activation energy and k_b is the Boltzmann constant. For this type of dependence, $\ln(R)$ is assumed to be linear on $1/T$, which is also seen in **Figure 2d–f** and confirmed by the coefficient of determination (R^2), which is higher than 0.99 for all sensors. The thermistor constant B (K) can be easily determined from the respective figures because it is equal to the directive of the straight line. The values of “B” are 2147.5, 1482.7, and 1507.2 K for materials G-B0.5, G-B1, and G-B2, respectively. This constant determines the sensitivity of a temperature sensor with respect to nonlinear dependence.

The “B” values of commercially available bulk-semiconductor temperature sensors range from 2000–5000 K.^[63] This constant is hardly used in scientific publications to compare the sensitivity of thermistors, e.g., graphene-based thermistors. Instead, the temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR), expressed by the following equation (Equation 2), is standardly used.

$$TCR = \frac{1}{R_0} \cdot \frac{R - R_0}{T - T_0} \quad (2)$$

where R_0 is the initial resistance at initial temperature T_0 (10 °C) and R is the resistance at temperature T (90 °C). The sensor with the G-B0.5 layer has the highest TCR, namely $-10.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$, while the remaining materials have similar TCRs of $-8.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $-8.63 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for G-B1 and G-B2, respectively (**Table 1**). Minus means a decreasing trend, i.e., NTC dependence. The TCR (absolute value) of the tested materials is more than twice as high as the widely used platinum temperature sensor with a TCR value of $3.92 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$. **Table 2** shows the comparison of the TCR parameter of graphene-based temperature sensors. It is not possible to compare the humidity dependence of these sensors because the authors do not provide this parameter.

The G-B2 sensor also exhibited very high stability. It can be seen from **Figure 3a** that the curves overlap. The black curve indicates the first sensor response, and the green curve shows the response of the same one after half a year. The largest difference between the curves is at 30 °C and when the

Figure 3. Parameters of the G-B2 sensor a) stability of the sensor after half a year b) dynamic sensor response to temperature step from 24.2 to 35.8 °C and back to 24.2 °C.

sensor returns to 25 °C after completing the cycle, namely 1.5% of the response, which is a maximum deviation of 1.3 °C. Figure 3b shows the response and recovery time of the G-B2 sensor when the temperature was step changed from ambient temperature (24.2 °C) to heating plate temperature (35.8 °C) and back. The response time was defined as the time necessary to achieve 90% of the full sensor response which lasted 8 s. Analogically, the recovery time was determined as the time required to reach 10% of the full sensor response and it lasted 7 s. These values indicate a fast sensor response to temperature changes.

While the work by Zunino et al.^[64] provides better TCR values (Table 2), the authors did not test the influence of humidity during the operation of their thermal sensor, which can have a detrimental effect, as we showed in our study. Given that their characterization techniques confirmed the presence of hydrophilic oxygen functional groups, we can presume that their performance would be highly affected by increased humidity. Our sensor has overcome this obstacle thanks to its design and the above-described mechanism, still yielding very high TCR values.

2.4. Humidity Dependences of the Sensors

The response of the sensor to relative humidity also varied significantly with the amount of benzylamine on the surface, see Figure 4. All sensors were tested over a humidity range from 20% RH to 80% RH with a step change of 10% RH. The sensor was left for 20 min at each humidity level to allow the response to stabilize. The response of all sensors naturally decreases, which means that as the RH increases, the resistance of the sensor decreases. The G-B0.5 sensor had the highest response to humidity change, which was -41.3% over the range tested. It should be noted that the sensor responded relatively quickly to the RH changes while being able to settle to constant resistance values within a short time. Furthermore, the sensor also exhibited good desorption capabilities. When the RH level was reduced, the water molecules were spontaneously desorbed, and the resistance returned to its original value. This is a prerequisite for a good humidity sensor. Unfortunately, there is a large temperature dependency (see Figure 2a) that would have to be compensated for by another temperature sensor when using this one to detect the humidity levels. The moisture dependence of the materials with higher BZA con-

tent is significantly lower, specifically -8.8% for G-B1 and -3.8% for G-B2. The response of these sensors also partially reproduces the change in the RH. The highest increase in the resistance of the G-B2 sensor was from 70% RH to 80% RH, namely 1.8%. In other words, in the range from 20% RH to 70% RH (typical humidity levels), the humidity variance is $\pm 1\%$, which is an error of ± 0.84 °C at 25 °C. The humidity dependence of the sensor at higher temperatures, specifically at 35 and 45 °C, is shown in Figure S9 (Supporting Information). As a result, the moisture dependence of the sensor decreased with an increasing BZA content in the graphene structure. Figure 4 shows that the G-B2-based sensor was almost insensitive to the change in the moisture level between 20% RH and 70% RH. The sensors show some hysteresis during the response to humidity (marked in Figure 4). The hysteresis was calculated as the difference in the response value at the same humidity level. The first value was obtained while the humidity level was increasing, and the second value while the humidity level was decreasing. The hysteresis increases toward higher RH values. For the G-B2 sample, the hysteresis at 70% RH was 1.7% in response, and at 20% RH only 0.57%. The hysteresis was caused by only partially spontaneous desorption of

Figure 4. Response of the sensors to step change stairs of relative humidity at 23 °C.

water molecules adsorbed on the surface of the material. During desorption at lower humidities, fewer water molecules interacted with the surface; therefore, there was room for the unbinding of molecules that were previously bound to the surface at higher RH levels. This led to lower hysteresis at a lower level of RH. All sample types were prepared from a fluorographene precursor. From the XPS analysis, it is clear, that in the G-B0.5 sample, a significant amount of fluorine remained in the graphene structure, rendering the material less conductive with a high amount of water binding groups, which are crucial properties for clarifying the moisture dependence of this sample. Fluorine is strongly electronegative and can easily form hydrogen bonds with water molecules through its hydrogen atoms. Both hydrogen atoms are therefore strongly bonded to the fluorine atoms. Water molecules bound in this way cannot move freely and form the first physisorbed layer on the surface of the fluorographene, with a high content of fluorine. When the relative humidity increases, the number of adsorbed water molecules also increases, and additional water layers are formed on the first layer. However, in these higher layers, the water molecules are bound by only a single hydrogen bond. They can be ionized by the applied electric field to form hydronium ions H_3O^+ , which serve as charge carriers. The so-called Grotthuss mechanism of proton hopping then mediates the charge transfer between water molecules.^[68] As a result, the resistance of the active layer of the sensor decreases as the RH level increases. As the amount of BZA is augmented in the synthesis, the fluorine atoms are progressively replaced with humidity-resistant BZA moieties, and, therefore, the moisture dependence of the sensor decreases, which can also be seen in Figure 4.

3. Conclusion

We have developed BZA-modified graphene-based temperature sensors that exhibited exceptional sensitivity to high temperatures ranging from 10 to 90 °C. These sensors also demonstrated minimal interference from humidity, eliminating the need for sensor encapsulation and ensuring high dynamics. The graphene derivatives, varying in the degree of functionalization controlled by the reaction time of fluorographene with BZA, were thoroughly characterized using three different microscopy techniques: Raman spectroscopy, FT-IR, and XPS. These analyses confirmed the successful binding of benzylamine to the graphene structure, enhancing the material conductivity and imparting the water-repellent properties. The graphene derivative with the highest benzylamine content exhibited heightened sensitivity to temperature changes, with a B-parameter comparable to commercially used semiconductor sensors and a TCR value over twice as high as that of a conventional platinum thermometer. Additionally, this sensor displayed near-inertness to applied humidity within a wide range of 20% to 70% RH. Graphene modified in this manner emerges as a compelling candidate for a simple and affordable yet highly sensitive temperature sensor, particularly not only for monitoring the internal conditions in manufacturing and handling facilities and buildings, but also in emerging applications involving fully printed and wearable electronics. The presented chemical approach offers new strategies for mitigating the interference in a wide range of sensing applications.

4. Experimental Section

Synthetic Protocol and Characterization Techniques—Reagents and Materials: Graphite fluoride (>61 wt.% F), BZA (assay >99%), and DMF ($\geq 98\%$) were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich. Acetone (pure) and ethanol (absolute) were purchased from Penta, Czech Republic. All chemicals were used without further purification. Ultrapure water ($18 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used for washings.

Synthetic Protocol and Characterization Techniques—Synthesis: Graphite fluoride (250 mg) was dispersed in 15 mL DMF and stirred using a magnetic stirrer at 800 rpm for 3 days in a glass flask. Then, the mixture was sonicated for 4 h (Bandelin Sonorex, frequency 35 kHz, effective power 160 W) while maintaining the temperature below 40 °C. Then, the mixture was left to stir overnight at 800 rpm. The next day, the respective amount of BZA (0.44, 0.88, 1.76, and 3.52 mL for samples G-B0.5, G-B1, G-B2, and G-B4, respectively, the number denotes the molar ratio of BZA with respect to the mols of the precursor) was added, and the dispersion mixture was heated at 100 °C for 72 h with a condenser and stirred at 800 rpm in an oil bath. After the reaction was finished, the mixture was let to cool down, and the washing was performed as follows: 3× DMF, 3× acetone, 3× ethanol, 2× hot water (80 °C), 3× cold water while separating the solid product from the solvents using centrifugation (Sigma 4–16K) at 13 000 rcf. The final dispersions of the materials were prepared with ultrapure water and freeze-dried for 4 days.

Synthetic Protocol and Characterization Techniques—Characterization Techniques: FT-IR were measured using an iS5 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Nicolet), equipped with the Smart Orbit ATR accessory with ZnSe crystal. A 20 μL of the material dispersion in distilled water was placed on a ZnSe crystal and left to dry in an ambient environment.

XPS was carried out using a Nexsa G2 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) spectrometer equipped with an Al K α source. The obtained data were evaluated using the Avantage software. Scanning electron microscopy using a Hitachi SU6600 instrument with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV was used for imaging the morphology of the samples.

The Raman spectra were obtained using a DXR Raman microscope, and the 633 nm excitation line diode laser was used.

A MetrohmAutolab PGSTAT128N apparatus (MetrohmAutolab B.V., Netherlands), operated through the NOVA software package (version 1.11.2), was employed for conducting cyclic voltammetry (CV) analyses on the G-B samples in a three-electrode configuration. The three-electrode system utilized commercially available Metrohm DropSens screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCE), with the working and counter electrodes being constructed from carbon ink and the reference electrode employing an Ag ink. The SPCEs underwent modification as follows: a 16 μL droplet of a powder suspension (2 mg mL^{-1}) was applied to coat the SPCE electrode surface, and was subsequently allowed to dry at room temperature to create a thin film. The experiments were performed at room temperature (22 ± 2 °C).

Sensor Fabrication: All the prepared materials in a powder form were mixed with demineralized water in a ratio of 30 mg in 1 mL. Further, these mixtures were treated in an ultrasonic bath for 4 h in order to homogeneously disperse the graphene flakes in the dispersion. The active sensor layers were formed from the prepared dispersions by two methods: i) airbrush–spray coating and ii) drop coating. The latter method was used only for the G-B0.5 sample, where a thicker layer of the material was needed due to the low electrical conductivity. The deposition was carried out on aluminum substrates (96% Al_2O_3) with interdigitated gold electrodes created on the substrate surface by the lift-off method. The width of the electrode fingers is the same as the electrode spacing, namely 50 μm (Figure S1, Supporting Information). The deposition of active layers using the airbrush–spray coating method allows the formation of thin and homogeneous layers as the dispersion falls on the substrate in very small droplets. The resulting layer thickness can be controlled either by the length of one spray and/or by the number of sprays. The substrate was placed on a hotplate and heated to the boiling point of the solvent in the dispersion, i.e., 100 °C (demineralized water). This allowed rapid evaporation of the solvent, which prevented the formation of inhomogeneities called “coffee rings” formed by slow evaporation of the solvent,

Scheme 1. a) Individual steps of graphene-benzylamine derivative synthesis via fluorographene chemistry and b) methodologies of sensor modification using the strategy of airbrush-spray coating (for samples labeled as G-B1 and G-B2) or drop coating (for sample labeled as G-B0.5).

during which the graphene particles can re-agglomerate. The deposition by drop coating and subsequent evaporation of the solvent took place at room temperature, when 20 μL of the dispersion was directly drop-casted onto the substrate. The resistivity of the samples was measured using the standard four-point method with a Jandel probe (more information can be found in Supporting Information). Step-by-step synthesis of the graphene-benzylamine derivatives using the fluorographene chemistry is depicted in **Scheme 1a** and further fabrication of the sensor via airbrush-spray coating and drop coating methodologies is illustrated in **Scheme 1b**.

Temperature and Humidity Tests: All temperature tests were conducted within a compact, in-house-developed measuring chamber. The temperature control was carried out using two Peltier elements arranged in a cascade, enabling us to adjust the temperature from 0 to 100 °C. To ensure rapid response to temperature fluctuations, the sensors were tightly attached across the entire surface of the sensor substrate to the Peltier cell. Throughout the measurements, the humidity inside the chamber was maintained at $40 \pm 1\%$ relative humidity (RH) to simulate a standard operating environment.

The gas test system consisted of mass flow controllers (Sierra Instruments), a water bubbler, and a test chamber used for relative humidity (RH) testing. A water bubbler was employed to create different RH levels within the range of 20–80% by setting the suitable ratio of the air flow through the bubbler and the flow of dry air. (For example, 40% RH at a flow rate of 1 L min^{-1} and temperature 25 °C is achieved by 620 mL of dry air and 380 mL of humidified air flowing through the bubbler). The resulting humidity level in the test chamber was verified by a commercial humidity sensor SHT31 (Sensirion Company). The temperature inside the chamber corresponded to the laboratory temperature of 23 °C, and the total airflow through the chamber was set at 1 L min^{-1} . Throughout all tests, an E4980A LCR meter (Agilent, Santa Clara, United States) to continuously measure the electrical resistance was employed. The sensors were linked to the LCR meter using a 4-wire method, with spring test probes securing the connections. An AC signal voltage of 0.25 V_{rms}, operating at a frequency of 1000 Hz, was applied during the measurements. To facilitate a meaningful comparison between the individual sensors, the resistance changes resulting from the varying temperature and humidity were converted to a relative change in resistance. The formula for the relative change in resistance is as follows (Equation 3):

$$\text{Response} = \frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \frac{R - R_0}{R_0} \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

where R (Ω) is the sensor resistance at the maximum value of the parameter under investigation ($T = 90$ °C for the temperature test; RH = 80% for the humidity test), and R_0 (Ω) is the sensor resistance at the minimum value of the parameter under investigation ($T = 10$ °C for the temperature test; RH = 20% for the humidity test).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

V.Š. and J.Š. contributed equally to this work. The work was supported from ERDF/ESF project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587). The authors also thank the Research Infrastructure NanoEnviCz, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic under Project No. LM2023066. The research was also supported by the European Regional Development Fund Operational Programme Research, Development and Education (OP RDE) Project “Carbon allotropes with rationalized nanointerfaces and nanolinks for environmental and biomedical applications” (No. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_026/0008382). This article was produced with the financial support of the European Union under the REFRESH – Research Excellence For REgion Sustainability and High-tech Industries project number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition. The authors gratefully acknowledge Emil Řemeslníček and Gifty Jacob for their assistance with the synthesis of the materials, Kateřina Roháčková for Raman measurement, Jan Pauswang for conducting of cyclic voltammetry and Vítězslav Hrubý for providing some of the FTIR data.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in ZENODO repository at [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1139723>], reference number 11397231.

Keywords

benzylamine, graphene, humidity, sensor, temperature

Received: February 12, 2024
Revised: June 7, 2024
Published online: July 2, 2024

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